

Project acronym: EVERSE
 Grant Agreement Number: 101129744
 Project full title: European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence
 Call identifier: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01

Milestone 8: First evaluation of the tools and services in the form of a workshop against WP2 initial best practices (MS4) and recommendations to adapt these tools if necessary.

Version: 1
 Status: Final
 Dissemination Level: Public
 Means of verification: Workshop
 Due date of milestone: 30.04.2025
 Actual submission date: 29.04.2025
 Work Package: 3
 Lead partner for this deliverable: UEDIN
 Partner(s) contributing: CERTH, NLeScience Center, LAPP, UPM

Main author(s):

Name: Elena Breitmoser	UEDIN
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Other author(s):

Thomas Vuillaume	LAPP, CNRS
Kirsty Pringle	UEDIN
Faruk Diblen	NLESC
Fotis Psomopoulos	CERTH
Nikos Pechlivanis	CERTH
Elena Bakoglidou	CERTH
Aspasia Orfanou	CERTH

Introduction

The online workshop “Evaluation of tools and services to improve the quality of research software” took place on Monday 10th February from 10 CET till 16 CET.

The goals of the workshop were to provide a platform for knowledge exchange and to foster discussion about relevant tools and services used to access and improve the quality of research software, including FAIRness. We wanted to capture existing practices across communities, offer a space where participants can learn from each other and identify gaps in available tooling.

Over 90 people registered their interest in the workshop in advance, with roughly over 40 attending on the day at its peak.

The organising committee consisted of:

- CERTH: Fotis Psomopoulos
- NL eScience Center: Faruk Diblen
- LAPP/CNRS: Azza Gamgami, Thomas Vuillaume
- UEDIN (lead): Elena Breitmoser, Kirsty Pringle, Neil Chue Hong
- UPM: Daniel Garijo

Implementation

The workshop started with two introductory sessions to introduce the wider background and allow the attendees to familiarise themselves with EVERSE in general and the aims of Work Package 3 (WP3) in particular. This was followed by a poll on people's backgrounds, interests and experience with software quality tools. We had three invited talks from Research Software Engineers, Mike Jackson from EPCC, and Steve Crouch and Philly Broadbent from SSI Southampton, who presented their favourite software quality tools in five-minute lightning talks to give examples of what software tools are used by experts in the field and why. This was followed by more interactive sessions with guided discussions in breakout sessions. The workshop ended with a wrap-up and reporting back from the various breakout sessions, giving the audience the opportunity to share with everyone what they had found most interesting or useful during the day.

The [indico invite](#) provides a short summary of the workshop goals, connection details and a link to the agenda and slides presented on the day.

Links to other EVERSE activities

The design and activities in the workshop drew from work completed by other EVERSE WPs.

- To inform the discussions we considered the [initial best practices from the MS4 survey](#).
- Their quality aspects for five out of the six research software quality dimensions (see [EVERSE RSQkit Reference Framework](#)) ‘usability’, ‘testing’, ‘documentation’, ‘performance’ and ‘security’ were used for breakout session 2 (see [spreadsheet](#)). The quality aspects were slightly re-phrased to improve clarity. The sixth research software quality dimension ‘functionality’ was not covered in the workshop because no quality aspects had been identified in the MS4 survey and only a total of three tools had been identified as linked to this quality dimension. Further investigation for the reasons might be of interest.
- The tools were chosen from the [list of tools gathered for D3.1](#) according to the quality dimensions assigned to them. To keep the exercise do-able within the given timeframe we concentrated on about ten tools for each research software quality dimension.
- We chose not to introduce the technical term of ‘software quality indicators’, as for example used for the Biohakathon (see <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ILLEsB7QZF32DeljFIDvCA70bvgG5QhsAZ9gZ6mCfLc/edit?usp=sharing>) to avoid confusion for non-EVERSE participants by introducing further technical terms. In addition, we did not adhere to the Biohakathon’s 17 super groups, which they equal to ‘software quality dimensions’.

Outcomes

All of the outcomes are obtained through interaction with the attendees, i.e. from a slido poll, breakout rooms with interactive discussions and parallel sessions on a variety of topics.

Slido poll session

The slido statistics showed that 40 out of 48 attendees voted in the slido poll. This number corresponds to all participants minus the eight organising committee members. The figures with the results show the actual number of voters for each of the questions asked.

The workshop participants came from a variety of countries across Europe and most of them consider themselves to be either mid-career (38%) or established (35%), only 24% had their first employment or were still in higher education (3%).

Most participants (56%) were not a member of one of the five EOSC Science Clusters of which Life Sciences (14%) and Astronomy & Particle Physics (11%) were most strongly represented and Social Sciences & Humanities least (3%).

Nearly half (45%) use software quality tools to assess or improve their software on a weekly basis. Most other users do so daily (19%), monthly (10%) or only a few times a year (10%) and 16% never do so.

Among the tools, which users have taken up using recently to improve the quality of their software, ‘Github repository’ (but also related tools like ‘Github actions’, ‘git copilot’, ‘gitlab’) and ‘chatGPT’ are followed by FAIR assessment tools like ‘somef’ and ‘howfairis’ and metadata tools like ‘codemeta’ and ‘CFF’. The biggest challenges when adopting new software quality tools seem to be quite diverse with the main issue being documentation.

Users find it most difficult to address the following software quality dimensions in their work: ‘usability’ was found most challenging, followed by ‘functionality’, ‘technical performance’ and ‘documentation/technical support’, with ‘testing’ coming out as least challenging.

Whereas users considered ‘functionality’ most important for their project (38%), then both ‘usability (23%) and ‘documentation/technical support’ (23%). ‘Technical performance’ and ‘testing’ were both ranked rather low with 8%, respectively, and no one considering ‘security’ to be important, which is quite an interesting result that so few users are interested in testing their code or optimising its performance.

Attendees’ most favourite software tools are:

- Github/gitlab (CI, Github Actions)
- AI tools (chatGPT, Claude, Cursor.ai, Blackbox.ai, Warp), also to give suggestions
- OpenSSF checklist for self-assessment
- Documentation (Docusaurus, Jupyter Notebooks)
- Grep
- Linter (Linter, Formatter)
- Sonarqube/sonacloud provide an extensive analysis of code quality, code smells, etc.
- Reuse.software

When asked which software quality dimensions from our list they feel are most undervalued, the following were mentioned:

- Security/Safety(6x)
- Usability (6x)
- Documentation (3x)
- Maintainability (2x)
- Resilience (2x)
- Support quality
- Performance

Breakout Sessions

The outcomes are mainly from breakout session 2, which consisted of five group discussions, each group focusing for 50 minutes on one of the six quality dimensions for research software as defined in the EVERSE RSQkit Reference Framework (apart from ‘functionality’). The description of the task can be found in our [public github](#). The sheet for each software quality dimension was filled in to various degrees by each of the five breakout groups, the results of which can be found in the [spreadsheet](#) used.

In several groups, participants identified many more tools than the ones we had listed in advance.

One participant raised the issue that none of the measures (what we call 'best practices') we list for e.g., ‘usability’ are according to the ISO standards (see <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/iso-iec-9126-in-software-engineering/>).

Issues, repeatedly encountered and recommendations given to other users are:

- Restricted time available to be able to find and assess usefulness of tool
- Rather complicated for beginners to navigate their way around finding suitable tools
- Many tools are rather complex
- Some tools are poorly documented, as well as some documentation being scarily extensive
- Learn about tool usage by copying from others
- Search within your community
- Use AI to answer questions
- Watch videos about tools

Often, non-native-English speakers prefer to use tools with documentation in their native language. There is the additional challenge to ensure that translations are precise and consistent and don’t obscure what the tool is meant to help with.

In the group focusing on the research software quality dimension of “Documentation” the overall discussion focused on the fact that while the tools were helpful, many relied on significant user input to add all the text, which is then pulled together by the tool. They highlighted the usefulness of tools that help to version control documentation and provide a DOI. None of the tools were able to automatically create user examples, though some did host examples once written. Overall, there were more tools that improve documentation, with only a couple giving some measurement of documentation.

Parallel Sessions

We offered three 45-minute, parallel sessions on the topics “TechRadar”, “Missing Tools” and “Personas”.

TechRadar

In this session there were 16 attendees. At the beginning, a survey to get feedback on what are the needs and what people would like as a TechRadar was done. The questions discussed were:

1. “What metadata on the tools and services should we collect?” (16 answers received)
 - a. The categories ‘Licence’ and ‘Version’ got 3 votes each.
 - b. The categories ‘Description’, ‘Citation’ and ‘Community: Who uses it so I can ask how they do it’ got 2 votes each.
 - c. One vote was given to the remaining categories.

2. “What metadata should be used to categorize and search for tools and services in a dashboard?” (13 answers received)
 - a. The metadata category ‘Programming language supported’ got 3 votes.
 - b. The metadata categories ‘Rating’, ‘Function: linter, testing, etc.’ and ‘License’ got 2 votes each.
 - c. One vote was given to the remaining metadata categories.

A conclusion drawn from the answers to the second survey question was that to categorize and search for software efficiently, a dashboard should focus on:

- Technical compatibility (to filter relevant tools)
- Functionality (to match use cases)
- Trust and maintenance (to assess reliability)

3. “What the dashboard should ideally look like?” The answers fall into the following three categories: “Tool Discovery and Exploration”, “Search and Filtering” and “User Experience and Interaction”.

We concluded that what users need is guidance and recommendation on tools! And there are too many and not enough time to explore them all. Hence, EVERSE should make opinionated recommendations. Users expect a structured, searchable, and interactive dashboard that helps them:

- Find tools based on function, compatibility, and use case.
- Assess tool reliability through metadata on community adoption, quality, and maintenance.
- Explore and discover new tools.
- Interact dynamically through advanced filters, rankings, and AI-assisted recommendations.

Missing Tools

EVERSE has compiled a list containing 76 tools to enhance software quality; this session aimed to identify tools missing from the list and to identify non-existent tools that would be beneficial. The group highlighted that creating documentation for software is very important, but that there isn’t a single overarching tool to create documentation, this is partly because many different

types of documentation are needed (e.g. technical guides to funder reports), but even if one focuses on a single type of documentation there is a lack of tools that can help. In terms of non-existent tools, participants said that an automated documentation debugger that identifies assumed knowledge gaps would be useful. The group also discussed translation barriers for non-English speakers, which remain a challenge as current translation technologies can introduce errors. Participants also highlighted the need for a readability checker that evaluates jargon complexity and reading levels for different audiences.

It was noted that workflow managers aren't included on the WP3 list of tools; selecting the right one is difficult, and a guidance tool akin to "Choose a License" for workflow selection could be beneficial.

One additional gap in tooling noted was the absence of a drag-and-drop tool for containerisation with Docker or Singularity, which would make it easier to manage dependencies and software environments. They noted that dependency tracking is well-covered by existing tools, but security analysis remains complex and fragmented.

Looking ahead to future tools, tools that assess energy efficiency and suggest optimisations would be useful, as well as solutions that streamline test generation. Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification (VVUQ) methods are essential for large-scale simulations, but comprehensive, automated tools for this purpose are scarce.

Finally, the group noted that one major recurring issue for the adoption of tools is the learning curve associated with existing tools—many useful solutions exist but are underutilised due to time constraints and lack of awareness.

Personas

In the personas session, there were four attendees, three of whom were EVERSE members. Despite the small group and limited time, excellent progress was made and the group developed some promising personas that will help shape the EVERSE pipelines.

Conclusions

The workshop and its high attendance confirm a strong interest in tools and services to improve the quality of research software in the wider research software community.

We identified several re-occurring themes. Users would like guidance and recommendations on tools, and EVERSE could support this need, even with opinionated recommendations. Time and steep learning curves are an issue, particularly when tools are complex and either extensively documented or not well documented at all. Another issue is offering tools in languages beyond English. Often, non-native-English speakers prefer to use tools with documentation in their native language. There is the additional challenge to ensure that translations are precise and consistent and don't obscure what the tool is meant to help with.

There were several recommendations on what the future dashboard should focus on.

Both the preparation of the workshop and running breakout session 2, illuminated the need to align definitions and dimensions across EVERSE, including the need to not neglect already existing definitions and standards.

EVERSE might want to understand why the software quality dimension “functionality” appears to be underrepresented compared to the five other ones, whereas “security” appeared to be of least importance and interest to the users, both visible from the poll and the lack of attendance of the breakout session dedicated to “security/safety”. We think there is a rather large gap between recognition of importance and interest. Often people have very little knowledge about security and do not know how and where to start. Tools that are very easy to use and make recommendations, rather than simply give a score, for improvement are essential.

The outcomes of this workshop can feed back into

- T3.2: How to integrate and consolidate the tools
- T3.3: The dashboard
- T5.3: The monthly series on tools and best practices to increase software quality
- The list of tools from D3.1
- The Reference Framework
- The overall discussion on the alignment issues across EVERSE

For this purpose, a more [detailed report](#) is available on zenodo.

After the workshop we asked all participants for their feedback. We received three replies in total to some or all of the following questions:

1. Usefulness of the workshop
2. What did you learn that you will be passing on to others?
3. Do you have any comments about the event organisation? What worked and what didn't work?
4. Do you have any other comments you'd like to provide?

